

USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Annotation; "innovative education" is capable of self-development and creates conditions for the comprehensive development of all its participants, and innovative education is a developing education. In this thesis is discussed about use of innovative technologies in educational process.

Key words; innovative, education, foreign languages, modern

Today, the interest and attention to the use of innovative technologies, pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process is growing day by day. One of the main reasons for this is that in traditional education, students are taught to acquire only ready-made knowledge, while modern technologies allow them to search for the acquired knowledge by themselves, study and analyze it independently and even draw their own conclusions will teach. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the development, formation, learning and upbringing of the individual. Therefore, the role and importance of modern teaching methods, innovative, pedagogical and information technologies in the preparation of teachers - qualified professionals. Based on this goal, implementation of the higher education process, improvement of educational work, implementation of modern pedagogic, innovative and information technologies in the educational process, popularization of advanced work practices, establishment of a community-based educational institution creating and strengthening cooperation between The process of turning scientific knowledge into innovation can be expressed as a sequential chain of

events, during which the innovation matures from an idea to a specific product, technology or service and is disseminated in practical use.

The modern content delivered to students include the development of science knowledge as much as the development of competencies relevant to modern knowledge practices. This content should be presented in the form of multimedia learning materials that are well structured and delivered using modern means of communication. Modern methods of teaching are not only based on passive perception of the material, but also active methods of forming competences based on the interaction of students and their involvement in the learning process. The quality of education is a set of consumer characteristics of the social system, process of state education and, as a result, the ability to meet the needs of the individual, society and the interests of society.

The unique aspect of the new relationship differs from the traditional education in that it does not prohibit the independence of students and educational activities, but directs them to the set goal, organizes educational activities in cooperation, and consciously directs them to activities, it is considered to increase students' interest in learning the basics of science by effectively organizing an activity without ordering it, and giving them the right to choose freely without limiting their needs, interests and capabilities.

Nowadays, the ability to know foreign languages is an integral part of education. Due to the high rate of cooperation with foreign partners among specialists in various fields, there is a high demand for them to learn the language. Success in achieving this goal depends on the practical methods and skills of teachers. The pedagogue has the ability to direct the acquired knowledge, skills, qualifications, teaching tools, modern pedagogical technologies in accordance with the purpose, and he determines the specific goal for the learner based on the state educational standards. This, in turn, leads to the development of a plan for the use of pedagogical technologies, that is, to the determination of their tasks. A dynamic model of education is created taking into account the set goals and tasks. The

development of the model is mainly based on the method of systematic approach, the creation of a system of goals and the sequence of its achievement. Creating an educational model is one of the main requirements of modern educational technology. The ability to use information technologies and modern teaching methods helps to quickly understand new materials. By combining different methods, the teacher is able to solve specific educational programs. In this regard, teachers and students should familiarize themselves with modern methods of teaching foreign languages. As a result, the ability to choose the most effective methods to achieve one's goals is formed. The use of several methods of teaching and learning will give effective results. Teaching is carried out in small steps and is based on the student's existing knowledge system.

As time progresses, innovations in every field are increasing. Different styles are also emerging in language teaching. A step-by-step approach to teaching English based on the learner's potential, level, and age gives good results. In this case, students are divided into groups based on teaching at the primary level, teaching at the middle level, and teaching at the higher level. A special program is developed by the teacher for each stage. While organizing a lesson based on innovative technologies, the teacher can use various technical tools (computer, projector, electronic board, etc.). The more there are innovations in the activity of the teacher, the more the content will increase. It should also be recognized that ideas about innovative technologies and interactive methods in education do not have a stable and perfect form. Each teacher can bring innovation to education individually. Innovative technologies arise from the teacher's dissatisfaction with his work.

Effectiveness as the most important sign of innovative methods is manifested only when positive achievements are achieved in the teacher's work. The technological, observability, and recording of results in measurements is demonstrated by evaluating new methods and methods of teaching. The important aspect of this measure is manifested in the unity of the formation of the person, his perception and concepts. In this regard, the innovative process can be considered as

the process of bringing the scientific idea to the stage of practical use and implementing changes in the social and pedagogical environment.

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